

Preparation of *s*-Triazinylaminophenylsulphones: Part I

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Manuscript received 11 December 1975; revised 6 April 1976, accepted 8 April 1976.

4-Aminodiphenylsulphone is condensed with cyanuric chloride at 0° to get *p*-(2,4-dichloro-*s*-triazin-6-yl-amino)-diphenylsulphone which was then condensed with different bases (one mole) to afford *s*-triazinylaminophenylsulphones (I).

SEVERAL derivatives and analogues of amino-sulphones have been shown to have strong tuberculostatic^{1,2}, antileprotic^{3,4}, anticonvulsant⁵ action. *s*-Triazine derivatives have also been the subject of several investigators as potential therapeutic agents for diseases due to bacteria and protozoa⁶, African sleeping sickness^{7,8}, malaria^{9,10}, cancer^{11,12}. Some of them possess antiviral property¹³ and are also used as fungicides^{14,15}, and weedicides¹⁶. Foye and Buckpitt¹⁷ carried out the condensation of cyanuric chloride with diamino thiazolyl phenylsulphone to prepare *s*-triazine derivatives. We have used this method to synthesise *s*-triazinylaminophenylsulphone of the type (I) with a view to study their therapeutic values.

(Type I)

where R₁ = Chloro, phenylamino, substituted phenyl-amino, pyridyl, piperidyl, etc.

R₂ = Chloro, amino.

4-Aminodiphenylsulphone was condensed with cyanuric chloride at 0° to get *p*-(2,4-dichloro-*s*-triazin-6-yl-amino)-diphenylsulphone which was then condensed with different bases (one mole), e.g., aniline, *o*-, *m*- and *p*-toluidine; *o*-, *m*- and *p*-chloroaniline, *p*-bromoaniline, *p*-iodoaniline; *o*-, *m*- and *p*-anisidine, *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitroaniline; α -naphthyl-amine, 2-aminopyridine; benzylamine and piperidine at 30°-35° using acetone or dioxane as solvent. The product was then treated with liquor ammonia to get the desired products (see Table).

Experimental

a) Preparation of *p*-(2,4-Dichloro-*s*-triazin-6-yl-amino)-diphenylsulphone

4-Aminodiphenylsulphone (0.01 mole) dissolved in acetone (40 ml) was added to a solution of cyanuric chloride (0.01 mole) in acetone (40 ml) at 0°. Contents were stirred for an hour with simultaneous addition of aqueous sodium hydroxide solution (10 ml, 4%) and diluted with ice water (100 ml). The product obtained was filtered, washed with water and dried. Physical constants are recorded in Table.

b) Preparation of *p*-(2-Arylamino-4-chloro-*s*-triazin-6-yl-amino)-diphenylsulphone

The amines (0.01 mole) dissolved in dioxane (10 ml) were added to the suspension of *p*-(2,4-dichloro-*s*-triazin-6-yl-amino)-diphenylsulphone (0.01 mole) in

TABLE. PREPARATION OF *s*-TRIAZINYLAMINOPHENYLSULPHONE OF TYPE (I)

	R ₁	R ₂	Yield %	M.P. °C	N %	
					Calcd.	Found
1.	Chloro	Chloro	77.42	290-91	14.18	14.30
2.	Anilino	Chloro	82.95	162-63	16.00	16.10
3.	Anilino	Amino	95.70	196-97	20.09	20.17
4.	<i>o</i> -Toluidino	Chloro	85.59	96-98	15.50	15.55
5.	<i>o</i> -Toluidino	Amino	94.69	220-22	19.45	19.55
6.	<i>m</i> -Toluidino	Chloro	89.21	122-23	15.50	15.58
7.	<i>m</i> -Toluidino	Amino	92.61	184-85	19.45	19.53
8.	<i>p</i> -Toluidino	Chloro	87.23	244-45	15.50	15.53
9.	<i>p</i> -Toluidino	Amino	95.23	273-74	19.45	19.56

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TABLE. PREPARATION OF *s*-TRIAZINYLAMINOPHENYLSULPHONE OF TYPE (I)—*contd.*

R ₁	R ₂	Yield %	M.P. °C	N %	
				Calcd.	Found
10. <i>o</i> -Chloroanilino	Chloro	88.98	205	14.64	14.90
11. <i>o</i> -Chloroanilino	Amino	95.32	250-52	18.57	18.65
12. <i>m</i> -Chloroanilino	Chloro	84.76	above 300 (d)	14.84	14.92
13. <i>m</i> -Chloroanilino	Amino	94.71	290	18.57	18.65
14. <i>p</i> -Chloroanilino	Chloro	86.88	212-13	14.84	14.90
15. <i>p</i> -Chloroanilino	Amino	96.32	200-2	18.37	18.68
16. <i>p</i> -Bromoanilino	Chloro	59.19	200	13.55	13.61
17. <i>p</i> -Bromoanilino	Amino	94.55	296-8	16.90	16.98
18. <i>p</i> -Iodoanilino	Chloro	82.17	205-6	12.43	12.51
19. <i>p</i> -Iodoanilino	Amino	95.59	above 300 (d)	15.44	15.51
20. <i>o</i> -Nitroanilino	Chloro	86.33	above 360 (d)	17.41	17.50
21. <i>o</i> -Nitroanilino	Amino	95.14	292	18.14	18.20
22. <i>m</i> -Nitroanilino	Chloro	70.49	290-2	17.41	17.48
23. <i>m</i> -Nitroanilino	Amino	88.55	above 300 (d)	18.14	18.22
24. <i>p</i> -Nitroanilino	Chloro	70.54	above 300 (d)	17.41	17.49
25. <i>p</i> -Nitroanilino	Amino	89.58	above 300 (d)	18.14	18.22
26. <i>o</i> -Anisidino	Chloro	80.25	238	14.97	15.05
27. <i>o</i> -Anisidino	Amino	95.12	above 300 (d)	18.75	18.83
28. <i>m</i> -Anisidino	Chloro	70.15	155	14.97	15.08
29. <i>m</i> -Anisidino	Amino	89.32	300 (d)	18.75	18.82
30. <i>p</i> -Anisidino	Chloro	75.22	175	14.97	15.05
31. <i>p</i> -Anisidino	Amino	88.32	285	18.75	18.80
32. 1-Naphthylamino	Chloro	86.16	145-46	14.36	14.43
33. 1-Naphthylamino	Amino	94.11	272-74	17.95	18.03
34. 2-Pyridylamino	Chloro	82.12	above 300 (d)	19.25	19.22
35. 2-Pyridylamino	Amino	95.48	above 300 (d)	23.42	23.50
36. Benzylamino	Chloro	77.54	229-30	15.50	15.58
37. Benzylamino	Amino	97.21	300 (d)	19.45	19.53
38. Piperidino	Chloro	74.29	242-44	16.29	16.37
39. Piperidino	Amino	95.61	292-94	20.48	20.56

Compound¹ gave correct C, H analysis.

dioxane (60 ml) at 30°-35°. A clear solution was obtained after an hour. Contents were stirred for an hour with the gradual addition of aqueous sodium hydroxide solution (10 ml, 4%) and diluted with ice water (100 ml). The product obtained was filtered, washed with water and dried. Similarly 2-amino-pyridine and piperidine were condensed. Physical constants are recorded in Table.

c) *Preparation of p*-(2-Arylamino-4-amino-*s*-triazin-6-yl-amino)-diphenylsulphone

Liquor ammonia (1 ml) was added to the solution of *p*-(2-arylamino-4-chloro-*s*-triazin-6-yl-amino)-diphenylsulphone (0.001 mole) dissolved in dioxane (20 ml) and refluxed in water bath at 80°-85° for 1½ hr. The contents were poured in crushed ice (100 g.). The product obtained was filtered, washed with water and dried. Similarly 2-aminopyridine and piperidine were condensed. Physical constants are recorded in Table.

Acknowledgement

Authors are thankful to Saurashtra University for research facilities.

References

1. N. RIST, F. BLOCH and V. HAMON, *Inn. Inst. Pasteur.*, 1940, **64**, 203.
2. N. RIST, *Compt. rend. soc. biol.*, 1939, **130**, 972-976.
3. G. H. FAGET and R. C. POGGE, *Public Health repts. (U.S.)* 1943, **58**, 1729.
4. R. G. COCHRANE, *Brit. Med. J.*, 1952, **2**, 1220.
5. S. ARCHER and M. S. SUTER, *U.S. Pat.*, 1952, **2**, 618, 637.
6. JENECH, U. S. P. 2, 092552.
7. E. A. H. FRIEDHEIM, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, **66**, 1775.
8. J. CONTROULIS, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, **66**, 1775.
9. W. W. CUTHBERTSON and J. S. MOFFATT, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 561.
10. F. H. S. CURD, J. K. LANDQUIST and F. L. ROSE, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 154.
11. E. CIORANESCU, *Rev. Chim. (Bucharest)*, 1954, **5**, 425.
12. J. H. BURCHENAL and S. F. JOHNSTON, *Proc. Soc. Exptl. Biol. Med.*, 1950, **74**, 788.
13. CIBA LTD., U.S.P. 282, 4088, 1950.
14. C. N. WOLF, U.S.P. 2, 720, 480, 1955.
15. C. N. WOLF, P. H. SCHULDT and M. M. BALSWIN, *Science*, 1935, **121**, 61.
16. J. R. GEIGY and BASEL SWITZ, *Exptl. (Germany)*, 1956, **12**, 146, 8.
17. W. O. FOYE and A. E. BUCKPITT, *J. Amer. Chem. Assoc. Sci. Educ.*, 1952, **41**, 387.